

Research Article

Sperm precedence pattern and the effect of irradiation on male mating competition in the oriental fruit fly, *Bactrocera dorsalis*

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Abstract

The sterile insect technique (SIT) is a feasible control strategy for the oriental fruit fly *Bactrocera dorsalis* (Hendel) (Diptera: Tephritidae) attacking diverse fruits. Our understanding for the sperm precedence pattern and mating competition of the irradiated males of *B. dorsalis* relative to the unirradiated ones is important for SIT program. Here we employed the sterile male technique to determine sperm precedence pattern and compare their mating competition between the irradiated and unirradiated males *B. dorsalis*. Our results indicated that the unirradiated males were significantly more competitive at mating over the irradiated ones. In twice-mated females the mating order between the irradiated and the unirradiated males had little effect on the number of eggs laid, but the proportion of the hatched eggs was significantly lower for females that mated first with an irradiated male than the females that mated first with a unirradiated male. There were significant differences in fecundity and fertility when females paired with various ratios of the irradiated males to the unirradiated ones. With the increase of the ratios of the irradiated males to the unirradiated ones, female fecundity and fertility gradually declined. It seems likely that SIT (sterile male technique) is promising for the control of the fruit fly *B. dorsalis*.

Keywords

Bactrocera dorsalis (Hendel); male mating competition; sterile insect technique; sperm precedence; irradiation

Introduction

The oriental fruit fly, *Bactrocera dorsalis* Hendel (Diptera: Tephritidae) is one of the most destructive quarantine insect pests of tropical and subtropical fruits and vegetables [1-6]. In particular, it has caused severe losses to carambola and mango in the southern and southwestern provinces and autonomous regions of China [6-7]. The sterile insect technique had been used as a component of area-wide integrated pest management for this pest [8-9] tried releasing sterile males to control the oriental fruit fly in mango orchards in Thailand. It indicated that these experiments are promising for the SIT program to control the fruit flies [8-9].

Multiple mating is a widespread phenomenon among diverse insects, in the tephritid fruit flies, where both males and females mate multiply [10-13]. Females of the oriental fruit fly are known to mate more than once throughout their lifetime [14-15]. Post copulatory sexual selection is found in a variety of animal taxa [16-18]. Post copulatory male-male competition occurs in the form of sperm competition [19-20], whereas post copulatory female choice is referred to as cryptic female choice [16,21]. In the Mediterranean fruit fly, *Ceratitidis capitata*, the pattern of sperm utilization revealed a clear advantage of the second male's sperm in siring progeny [22]. However, there is no report about the pattern of sperm

utilization by females of the polyandrous oriental fruit fly *B. dorsalis*.

Additionally, mating competition of irradiated males is of importance in evaluating the sterile insect technique (SIT) for controlling the oriental fruit fly. In general, irradiation has deleterious effects on male quality and mating competition of mass-reared flies used in SIT, such as *Ceratitidis capitata* [23-24], *Anastrepha obliqua* [25], and *Anastrepha ludens* [26]. To our knowledge, there is little report about the mating competition between the unirradiated and irradiated males of the polyandrous oriental fruit fly *B. dorsalis*.

In the present study, we irradiated the oriental fruit fly *B. dorsalis* with a dose of 95 Gy, a dosage widely used on orchard in China to sterilize the male flies [27]. We first aimed to determine sperm precedence pattern, and male mating competition between the irradiated and unirradiated males. Second, we evaluated the effects of different ratio of the irradiated males to the unirradiated ones on female reproductive output. Our understanding of the relevant information may to some extent shed some light on the controlling of the oriental fruit fly prior to our releasing sterile males to control the oriental fruit fly.

Materials and Methods

Insect preparation

Insects used in the present study were obtained from host guava plants (*Psidium guajava* L.) in the outskirts of Guangzhou, China and reared on artificial diets in the laboratory for three generations [28-29]. During the experiment, larvae were reared under the conditions of 25 ± 2 °C, 705% relative humidity (RH) and 12:12D:L light period. Two days prior to fly emergence, pupae were dyed with orange fluorescent dye (4 g dye per litre pupae) [30], and the dyed pupae were irradiated with a dose of 95 Gy using a ^{60}Co -irradiator. Upon emergence, flies were separated into metal screened cages (57 X 40 X 40 cm, *l:w:h*) based on their sex, and supplied with sugar : protein hydrolysate (3:1), water, and a piece of orange. In the afternoon of the mating day, 11-day-old females and males were introduced into an orbicular clear plastic cup or metal screened cages [31].

Sperm precedence pattern

Mating activity of *B. dorsalis* is restricted to an approximately 1-h long period immediately preceding sunset [32-33]. Two virgin males of different treatments, one including two unirradiated males, and the other including two irradiated males, were separately paired with a virgin female in an orbicular clear plastic cup (20 cm high, 7 cm diameter) with a piece of orange, male copulation were observed. The sexual interaction between male and female were observed from 15:00 to 21:00. The pairs entering into copulation were recorded and allowed to separate naturally and then the females that successfully mated were collected, and the females that failed to mate were removed from subsequent experiment. On the following day, the females that had copulated with a irradiated male were paired with the unirradiated males or vice versa. So there were two mating treatments for females: (1) first mating with unirradiated males and then with irradiated males (NI); (2) first mating with irradiated males and then with unirradiated males (IN). The females mated twice were kept individually. There were 10 replicates in each mating treatment. Eggs laid by the females mated twice were collected and counted every 3 days, there were over 9 gonotrophic cycles to collect the eggs. The eggs were maintained on the lab conditions as described above and left to determine the percentage of eggs hatched. Each treatment replicated 10 times.

Effect of irradiation on male mating competition

For determining the mating competition between the irradiated (I) and the unirradiated (N) males, two males (an irradiated male and a unirradiated male) and one female were used 15 days after emergence. The fruit fly does not reach sexual receptivity until 10-15 days post-emergence. Two virgin males (an irradiated male and a unirradiated male) and a virgin female were paired in an orbicular clear plastic cup (20 cm high, 7 cm diameter), covered with cotton gauze. We observed their sexual interaction between two males and one female from 15:00 to 21:00. A total of 60 pairs were observed. Mating pairs were collected with glass vials and the status of

the mated males were later identified by using a stereomicroscope, to detect the presence of dye in the ptilinum (area between the eyes) (Ohto et al. 1986; Chang and McInnis 2008). There were a total of 60 replications in male mating competition.

Effects of the ratios of the irradiated males to the unirradiated ones on female fecundity and fertility

In order to evaluate the effects of different ratio of the irradiated males to unirradiated ones on female reproductive output, we grouped the irradiated (I) and the unirradiated (U) males (total 12 males in each group) as following ratios: 3:9, 6:6, 9:3, 12:0, and 0:12, respectively. Each group was replicated 3 times and paired in (57.5 X 40 X 40 cm) screen cages with 12 virgin females. Eggs laid were collected and counted every 3 days, and there were over 9 gonotrophic cycles. The eggs were maintained on the lab conditions as described above and left to determine the percentage of eggs hatched. Each treatment was replicated three times.

Statistical analysis

Data were first checked for unirradiatedity and transformed when necessary to meet the assumptions of unirradiated distribution. The percentage of egg hatching was arcsine-square root transformed before analyses. The effects of different ratios of irradiated (I) to the unirradiated (N) males on total eggs laid and eggs hatched were tested by repeated-measured analysis of variance (ANOVA). Tukey's test was used to separate treatment means if the main effect was found to contribute significantly. Statistical analyses were performed using SPSS soft packages (version 13.0; SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA).

Results

Sperm precedence pattern and female fecundity

The results of the sperm precedence pattern indicated that the total eggs laid by the mated females (NI) and the females (IN) were 234.8 and 243.5, respectively. There was no significant difference in female fecundity between the two mating treatments (repeated-measured ANOVA: $F_{1,4}=0.154$, $P=0.715$, Fig. 1).

Figure 1. Eggs laid by the twice-mated *Bactrocera dorsalis* females with different mating order between the unirradiated (U) and the irradiated (I) males

In contrast, the proportion of eggs hatched of the twice-mated females (NI) and the females (IN) was 71.7% and 54.9%, respectively. The proportion of eggs hatched of the former was significant higher than the latter (repeated-measured ANOVA: $F_{1,4}=1222.133$, $P<0.0001$, Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Proportion of eggs hatched of the twice-mated *Bactrocera dorsalis* females with different mating order between the unirradiated (U) and the irradiated (I) males. Different letters indicating significant difference.

Effect of irradiation on male mating competition

When an irradiated and a unirradiated male were directly paired with a virgin female, Forty seven females successfully copulated. Of the copulated 47 females, 13 females copulated with the irradiated males, and 34 females copulated with the unirradiated males. The copulating success of the unirradiated males was significantly higher than that of the irradiated ones ($\chi^2=15.424$, $df=1$, $P<0.0001$, Fig. 3).

Figure 3. The first mating of females *Bactrocera dorsalis* with the unirradiated (U) and the irradiated (I) males. Different letters indicating significant difference.

Effects of the ratios of the irradiated males to the unirradiated ones on female fecundity and fertility

The effects of different ratios from 12:0, 9:3, 6:6, 3:9, to 0:12 of the unirradiated male to the irradiated one on female reproductive output were shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. Our results demonstrated that the number of eggs laid decreased with the proportion of irradiated males increased (Fig. 4). The total number of eggs of the ratio of N:I 12:0 and 9:3 was

significantly greater than that of the treatment I:I 12 (repeated-measured ANOVA: $F_{4,10}=6.556$, $P=0.007$, Fig. 4).

Figure 4. Eggs laid by *Bactrocera dorsalis* females with different ratios (U:I) between the unirradiated (U) and the irradiated (I) males. Different letters indicating significant difference.

The proportion of eggs hatched with different ratios of N:I from 12:0, 9:3, 6:6, to 3:9 was 90%, 81.1%, 64%, and 34.5%, respectively. With the decrease of the ratio of unirradiated males relative to the irradiated ones, the proportion of eggs hatched significantly and gradually decreased (repeated-measured ANOVA: $F_{3,8}=976.954$, $P<0.0001$, Fig. 5). The fertility of the females mated with two irradiated males were zero.

Figure 5. Proportion of eggs hatched of *Bactrocera dorsalis* females with different ratios (U:I) between the unirradiated (U) and the irradiated (I) males. Different letters indicating significant difference

Discussion

In the present study, although *B. dorsalis* females produced similar eggs after mating sequentially with two males (one the irradiated and the other unirradiated male), the proportion of eggs hatched of the females that mated first with a unirradiated male was significantly higher than that of females that mated first with a sterile male. This suggests that the first male fertilizes significantly more ova of the female than the second male. This also suggests an important role of the number of sperm from each male in postcopulatory sexual selection. The results strong suggest that the first sperm precedence occurs within the female spermathecae, as sperm utilization was significantly affected by male mating

sequence. The mechanism underlying the first sperm precedence may be due to male-male competition and/or female cryptic choice. The irradiated sperm competed greatly lower than the unirradiated sperm. This is unlike *Ceratitidis capitata*, which showed sperm precedence of the last male [22]. For *Bactrocera cucurbitae* when the interval between the first and the second mating was short (1-4 days), the irradiated sperm was considered to have an ability to compete well with the unirradiated sperm (Yamagishi et al. 1992). Although field data are lacking, Shelly (2000) [35] found that *B. dorsalis* females have a fairly high incidence of re-mating in the laboratory. Using the offspring of wild flies, we found that *C. capitata* female remating increased significantly under a highly male-biased sex ratio. Therefore, sperm precedence pattern has significant effect on SIT. The pattern of no male sperm precedence might be important for releasing the sterile males against the oriental fruit fly. Females successfully mating with an irradiated male, regardless of the male mating order, would substantially decrease the proportion of eggs hatched.

The major factor that affects the outcome of SIT is the mating competition of the sterile males relative to the unirradiated males. Our observation revealed that of 47 copulated females, 13 mated with the irradiated males, and 34 mated with the unirradiated males. These results strongly indicated that the sterile males had less mating competition than the unirradiated males, as has been found in previous studies [36-38]. The proportion of eggs hatched decreased as the ratio of the irradiated males to the unirradiated males increased. Hasan (1999) [39] also found *Tribolium freemani* and *T. destructor* infertility increased as the ratios of irradiated males increased to the unirradiated males and females. Although females preferred mating with unirradiated males, when more sterile males are present they are forced to mate with the sterile males as would be the case when a large number of sterile males are released in the SIT program at the target area. In our present study, with the increase of the ratio of irradiated males relative to the unirradiated ones, the proportion of eggs hatched significantly and gradually decreased. It seems likely that the efficiency of the SIT could be improved by increasing the ratio of sterile males relative to the wild males.

The sterile insect technique (SIT) can be a powerful method for pest control without the negative environmental effects of conventional pesticides [40], reducing the exposure of and harmful effects on non-target organisms. The data presented herein, provide useful information to ensure the effectiveness of a SIT program against the oriental fruit fly.

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